

Nomophobia Among B.Ed Students in relation to Demographic Variables

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Kamini Sehgal

Principal
Education
M.K. College Of Education
ShahpurJalandhar, India

Balwinder Nagpal

Assistant Professor
Education
M.K. College Of Education
Shahpur, Jalandhar, India

Abstract

Nomophobia (NO-Mobile Phone-PHOBIA) is the fear of being without a mobile phone, a growing concern in the digital era. With increasing smartphone usage, nomophobia has become a significant psychological and behavioral issue, particularly among younger individuals. This study aimed to assess the prevalence of nomophobia among smartphone users pursuing B.Ed course. The study found no significant difference between rural and urban area students and rural and urban area unmarried students. Only significant difference was found between married rural and urban area students.

Keywords

Nomophobia (NO-Mobile Phone-PHOBIA), Demographic Variables, B.Ed Students.

Introduction

Information and communication technologies have been an obligatory part of today's world. Smartphones are the most widely used technology (Vogels et al., 2022). Its usage rates have increased drastically, particularly during last ten years, among all age groups with the widening of Internet usage across the globe (International Telecommunication Union, 2022). The easy accessibility of technology and its facility feature of reacting to daily occasions without exerting extra effort are known to cause irrational technology usage problems, specifically in adolescents, along with emergence of novel bio-psycho-social health risks (Peris et al., 2020; Sharma et al., 2019). One of the emerged health risks regarding smartphone usage in digitalized world is nomophobia (Yildirim and Correia, 2015).

Objective of study

The present study was undertaken with the following objectives.

1. To investigate the significance of difference of nomophobia levels of rural and urban area B.Ed. students.
2. To investigate the significance of difference of nomophobia levels of unmarried rural and urban area B.Ed. students.
3. To investigate the significance of difference of nomophobia levels of married rural and urban area B.Ed. students.

Review of Literature

Nomophobia, the acronym of *no-mobile-phone-phobia*, is described as the fear experienced by an individual due to inability to access a mobile device, particularly a smartphone (Yildirim and Correia, 2015). Nomophobia is recognized as one of the notable behavioral addiction problems and is formally defined as a digital disorder (Bragazzi and Del Puente, 2014). Adolescents are believed to be the most vulnerable groups regarding nomophobia (Rodríguez-García et al., 2020). In an India-based study, 41% of the adolescents demonstrated nomophobia behaviors, and 21.7% had moderate-level nomophobia (Sharma et al., 2019). In a study conducted in the Philippines, 60.9% of adolescents showed moderate and 22.7% severe levels of nomophobia behaviors (Buctot et al., 2021). In Turkiye-based studies, approximately 50% of high school students were found to have moderate levels of nomophobia behavior (Eren et al., 2020; Teker & Yakşi, 2021).

Yildirim and Correia (2015) developed a 20 items scale to assess the severity of nomophobia and Identified and the four dimensions 1. Not being able to communicate 2. Loosing connectedness, 3. Not being able to access information 4. Giving up convenience. The psychological factors involved with over usage of mobile phone are low self-esteem and extrovert personality. We cannot ban using the mobile phones or smartphones but still we can limit our use and exposure to them. (Bhattacharya, Bashar, Srivastava & Singh 2019). Hawi and Samaha (2016) conducted a study through an online survey for the university students and found both male and female university students equally susceptible to smartphone addiction and it affects their academic performance. A cross sectional survey also found nomophobia vital in undergraduate medical students. (Kar, Sarma, Mistry and Pal, 2017). Anshari (2019) examined the prevalence of nomophobia among youth and how to overcome it and findings showed that nomophobia is related to other traits ranging from social, physiological and physical symptoms which encapsulate to smartphone dependency and also observes impact of nomophobia on personal habits and behaviors amongst the youngsters. In another study of 364 students, 62 have mild, 234 have moderate and 68 have severe nomophobia and a weak positive correlation between nomophobia and sleeping difficulty and anxiety was found. (Veerapu, N. et al. (2019). Almost two-third, adults are grappled with mobile phone addiction.

Notably, this dependence was more pronounced among the middle class. Many individuals primarily use their mobile phones for communication and social media, with lesser emphasis on academic and general purposes. (Balamurugan.et.al (2024). Buctot et al. (2021) studied, adolescents experiencing family dysfunction may exhibit higher levels of smartphone addiction and nomophobia. This indicates that the stability and quality of the family environment can impact how young individuals use and depend on their mobile devices.

Statement of the problem

Nomophobia among B.Ed Students in relation to Demographic Variables.

Hypothesis

1. There is no significant difference between nomophobia level of rural and urban area B.Ed students
2. There is no significant difference between nomophobia level of unmarried rural and urban area B.Ed. students.
3. There is no significant difference between nomophobia level of married rural and urban area B.Ed. students.

Methodology

In the present study descriptive method was used by the investigator to study Nomophobia among B.Ed. students.

Sampling

To conduct the present study random sampling technique was used. The sample contains 152 students pursuing B.Ed. course in Jalandhar District belonging to rural and urban area.

Analysis

Table 1:- Difference between Nomophobia level of rural and urban area students

Marital Status	Area	N	Mean	S.D	T-ratio	Significance
Unmarried	Rural	56	114.45	28.9	2.85174	Significant
	Urban	47	98.13	28.95		

Table 1 represents the values of Mean, S.D. and t ratio. As seen from the table the mean value of rural area students is 113.73 and mean value of urban area students is 101.91 and standard deviation of rural area students is 10.66 and urban area students is 10.09. The calculated t-value is **2.66314** is significant at the 0.01 level which indicates a highly significant difference between the groups. Hence, the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference between nomophobia level of rural and urban area B.Ed. students is rejected.

Table 2:- Difference between Nomophobia level of unmarried rural and urban area students

Area	N	Mean	S.D	T ratio	Significance
Rural	70	113.73	10.66	2.66314	Significant
Urban	82	101.91	10.09		

Table 2 represents the values of Mean, S.D. and t ratio. The mean value of rural area unmarried students is 114.45 and mean value of urban area unmarried students is 98.13 and standard deviation of rural area unmarried students is 28.9 and urban area unmarried students is 28.95. The calculated t-value is 2.85174 is significant at the 0.01 level which indicates a highly significant difference between nomophobia level of unmarried rural and urban area students. Hence, the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference between nomophobia level of unmarried rural and urban area B.Ed. students is rejected.

Table 3:- Difference between Nomophobia level of married rural and urban area students

Marital Status	Area	N	Mean	S.D	T-ratio	Significance
Married	Rural	12	110.42	27.77	-0.4268	Not significant
	Urban	34	107.21	20.3		

Table 2 represents the values of Mean, S.D. and t ratio. The mean value of rural area married students is 110.42 and mean value of urban area married students is 107.21 and standard deviation of rural area married students is 27.77 and urban area married students is 20.3. The calculated t-value is -0.4268 which is not significant at the 0.01 level which indicates no significant difference between nomophobia level of married rural and urban area students. Hence, the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference between nomophobia level of married rural and urban area B.Ed. students is accepted.

Conclusion

The results of the study are as under

1. There is significant difference between nomophobia level of rural and urban area B.Ed. students.
2. There is significant difference between nomophobia level of unmarried rural and urban area B.Ed. students.
3. There is no significant difference between nomophobia level of married rural and urban area B.Ed. students

Educational Implications

The present study is a step towards measure of nomophobia level of B.Ed. students residing in urban area and rural area. It may help teachers, parents and administrators to promote efficient and healthy use of mobile technology in learning spaces, in order to avoid the emergence of nomophobia and its consequences

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